

On the Possibility of Extending the Working Temperature Range of Silicon Integral Mechanical Transducers.

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Abstract

The article considers the necessity of expanding the operational capabilities of mechanical sensors for the further development of science and technology. To solve the problem of extending the operating temperature range above $+100^{\circ}\text{C}$ for integral mechanical transducers with an insulating p-n junction, experimental studies are needed to optimize the design, fabrication technology, and metrological capabilities. In addition, the paper discusses the development of a dielectrically insulated sensor using SOI technology. Research and development in this area are ongoing and are aimed at overcoming the problems associated with the limited operating temperature conditions and improving the metrological characteristics of the SOI.

Further development of science and technology requires a significant expansion of the operational capabilities of mechanical sensors. Promising for this purpose is the work associated with the creation of high-temperature integrated piezoresistive transducers (IPT). Semiconductor integrated transducers (IPTs) surpass traditional conductive transducers in most technical and economic aspects ¹. However, there are several challenges that hinder the development in this field, with the main one being limited operating temperature conditions. The majority of IPTs currently available are designed to operate at low temperatures, up to $+100^{\circ}\text{C}$. Yet, by improving insulation quality, it is possible to extend the upper limit to temperatures restricted by the onset of material's intrinsic conductivity or the plastic deformation of the elastic element. Primarily, it is advisable to investigate the potential for expanding the operating temperatures of IPTs with silicon-based piezoresistors. Due to their well-studied characteristics, advantageous physical properties, and technological compatibility, silicon remains unrivaled by any other semiconductor.

The wide possibilities for expanding the operating temperature range of IPTs (Integrated Passive Transducers) have been opened up by modern advancements in microelectronic technology. Among the currently used methods of dielectric isolation, silicon-on-sapphire (SOS) technology ² and silicon-on-insulator (SOI) technology ³ are of particular interest.

Based on the SOS (Silicon-on-Sapphire) technology, IPTs with dielectric isolation are being successfully developed, which are characterized by [2]:

- high metrological characteristics;
- high technological feasibility, particularly for flat elastic elements;
- excellent dielectric isolation between tensor resistors and elastic elements;
- operation within a temperature range up to the limit of silicon's intrinsic conductivity.

The development of IPTs with silicon elastic elements and silicon piezoresistors, interconnected and isolated from each other by a dielectric layer with a coefficient of linear thermal expansion (CLTE) matching, is considered promising ⁴. The main technological operations for their fabrication are based on the process of creating integrated circuits with dielectric isolation using the silicon-on-insulator (SOI) method.

The advantages of IPT-SOI include:

- utilization of technologically advanced methods such as chemical etching for shaping;
- application of diffusion or ion implantation technology combined with other microelectronics processes;
- creation of a structure in IPT with a matched coefficient of linear thermal expansion (CLTE);
- possibility of using electro-adhesive bonding to connect IPT with the sensor housing.

It should also be noted that the influence of the isolating properties of the p-n junction on the metrological characteristics of IPT at temperatures above +100°C is not sufficiently studied, and the actual operational limits are not defined. Therefore, the investigation of possibilities for expanding the operating temperature range for IP with a p-n junction is an open question.

All the presented approaches do not exclude each other but complement one another, and therefore, they should be developed in parallel. SOS converters have obvious operational advantages, but silicon converters are more economically beneficial. Therefore, the question of expanding the upper limit of the temperature range for IPT with a p-n junction and the development of new solutions like SOI remains relevant.

1 IPT with Insulating P-N Junction

IPT with an isolating p-n junction have advantages due to the well-developed manufacturing technologies and the merits of silicon as a material for the elastic element. Currently, IP with a p-n junction operates in the range of $\pm 60^\circ\text{C}$, and therefore, it may be practically important to expand their operating range in the positive temperature region without switching to new materials or insulating substrates. A theoretical model that allows analyzing the characteristics of p-n junction-based piezoresistors at elevated temperatures is discussed in reference ⁵. However, this question is still insufficiently explored from a practical perspective.

Let us consider the a priori information on this issue. The metrological characteristics of the bridge measuring circuit and the upper limit of the working temperature range of *IPT* with a p-n junction depend on the leakage currents of the piezoresistors and the shunt effect of the elastic element.

The temperature dependence of the resistance of an integrated piezoresistor is determined by the temperature-induced changes in the resistance of the resistive layer, R_{ch} , and the resistance of the "p-n junction - substrate (elastic element)", R_{sh} .

$$R_{in}(T) = \frac{R_{ch}(T)}{1 + \frac{R_{ch}(T)}{R_{sh}(T)}} \quad (1)$$

According to [5], express the temperature dependence of R_{ch} and R_{sh} as

$$R_{ch} = R_0 [1 + \alpha_0 (T - T_0)] \quad (2)$$

$$R_{sh} = \frac{2 \cdot V_{in}}{I_{rev0} W^2 L} e^{-\beta(1 - \frac{T_0}{T})} \quad (3)$$

where: R_0 is the resistance of the piezoresistor under normal conditions, α is the temperature coefficient of the resistive layer of the piezoresistor, which has a positive sign in the temperature range of $0^\circ\text{C} \div 200^\circ\text{C}$; β - the coefficient depending on the law of increasing reverse current. According to Table II in ⁶, it is determined by the approximate value of $\beta = (37 \div 39)$. I.e. $I_{rev} = I_{rev0} \cdot e^{38 \cdot (\frac{T-293}{T})}$; I_{rev0} is the initial value of the reverse current; L is the number of squares in the piezoresistor channel; W is the width of the piezoresistor channel; V_{in} is the voltage supplied to the piezoresistor.

As the temperature increases, the resistance of the piezoresistive layer increases, while R_{sh} decreases due to the exponential growth of the reverse current of the p-n junction. The appearance of a maximum on the temperature dependence curve $R_{in} = f(T)$ can be considered as the upper limit

of the piezoresistor's functionality, denoted as T_{max} . The position of the maximum is determined by the condition $\frac{dR_{in}}{dT} = 0$.

$$2 \ln \left[\frac{T_0}{T} + \alpha_0 T_0 \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T} \right) \right] + \beta \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T} \right) = \ln \frac{2V_{in}\alpha_0 T_0}{\rho_{ch} L^2 \beta I_{rev0} W^2} \quad (4)$$

where ρ_{ch} is the resistivity of the resistive layer of the piezoresistor ; T_{max} the greater the right-hand side of equation (4).

Figure 1: Components of leakage current (reverse current) I_{rev} and its areas of occurrence

The most noticeable influence has the initial value of the reverse current I_{rev0} . The reverse current of the p-n junction, or the reverse current of the I-V characteristic (I_{rev}), can be divided into three components ⁶ (See Figure 1):

I_{0gen} - the current generated by charge carriers in the depleted region of the p-n junction within the volume of the elastic element. I_{Sgen} - the current generated by charge carriers in the depleted region of the p-n junction on the surface of the elastic element. I_d - the diffusion component of the reverse current. Therefore, the total reverse current is given by the equation:

$$I_{rev} = I_{0gen} + I_{Sgen} + I_d \quad (5)$$

The main contribution at temperatures up to $+100^\circ C$ is made by the component I_{Sgen} . The density of this current is $(0.08 \div 1.6) \times 10^{-4} A \cdot m^{-2}$.

The upper limit of the operating range also depends on the voltage applied to the piezoresistor. As the V_{in} increases, R_{sh} increases, reducing the influence of the resistance of the elastic element. The increase in R_{sh} leads to a shift of T_{max} towards higher temperatures. However, this effect is observed under limited conditions, depending on the magnitude of the breakdown voltage of the p-n junction.

The highest value of T_{max} corresponds to the configuration where there is no reverse bias potential applied, i.e., "piezoresistor-substrate (elastic element)" with $V_{ch-ee} = 0$. Increasing the reverse bias potential leads to an increase in I_{rev} .

Figure 2 shows plots of dependence of R_{in} (input resistance), sensitivity coefficients and normalized null output on temperature for transducers made according to ⁷.

To solve the problem of extending the operating temperature range above $+100^\circ C$ for IPT with p-n junction experimental studies are required to optimize the design, manufacturing technology and evaluation of metrological capabilities.

2 IPT with Dielectric Isolation

Based on the analysis of existing technological capabilities ¹, existing design solutions ⁸, and the experimental verification of several technological approaches, it can be concluded that it is possible to develop IPT with a dielectric insulation of monocrystalline piezoresistors using a low-temperature

Figure 2: Temperature dependence of parameters *IPT* made according to *to*¹⁷ : (a) R_{in} - input resistance of full bridge measuring circuit (*MC*) ; R_{sh} - resistance "p-n junction - substrate (elastic element)" (b) K_{mc0} - normalized zero output of *MC*; K_{mc}^v - bridge sensitivity when *MC* is fed with stabilized voltage $V_{in} = 5$ V; K_{mc}^i - bridge sensitivity when *MC* is fed with stabilized current $I_{in} = 5$ mA.

glass layer on a monocrystalline silicon elastic element. To develop SOI-type *IPT*, it is necessary to address the challenges primarily associated with developing the silicon-glass-silicon structure and then optimize the design and technological solutions to ensure metrological characteristics comparable to existing *IPTs*. Figure 3 illustrates the structure of such a transducer⁹.

The sequence of manufacturing operations is as follows. Two silicon wafers of n-type (p-type can also be used) oriented in the plane (100) are used. Diffusion piezoresistive p^+ -type channels of $(2 \div 2.5)\mu m$ depth are formed on wafer A using oxidation, photolithography and boron diffusion operations (to doping levels greater than $1 \times 10^{19} cm^{-3}$). Also formed p^+ -type diffusion contact regions with a depth of $(5 \div 6)\mu m$ and chemical anisotropic etching of alignment marks as recesses at $(5 \div 6)\mu m$. On one side of wafer *Wafer*₁, where the diffusion channels are formed, and on either side of wafer *Wafer*₂, a layer of glass with a thickness of $(0.8 \div 1.2)\mu m$ is deposited using spin coating from an alcohol suspension. Subsequently, the wafers are aligned with each other along the base cuts and fused together under a slight pressure at a temperature of $(750 \div 800)^\circ C$. Using a 25% solution of *KOH*, wafer *Wafer*₁ is etched until the alignment marks and diffusion contacts become visible. The reverse side of *Wafer*₂ is etched anisotropically to form the required configuration of the elastic elements. Then, using photolithography and isotropic chemical etching processes, resistors are defined, consisting of a piezoresistive channel with a thickness of $(2 \div 2.5)\mu m$ surrounded by a protective layer of *Wafer*₁ material with a thickness of $(2.3 \div 3.5)\mu m$. It is also possible to leave areas of silicon from *Wafer*₁ underneath the conductive tracks and contact pads, as shown in Figure 4 (B). Aluminum is deposited on the side of the piezoresistors through thermal evaporation in a vacuum, and using photolithography, current-carrying tracks and contact pads are formed. After the annealing process, the wafers are separated into individual *IPT* crystals.

The layer of *Wafer*₁ material with resistance R_w and thickness H_w is intended to protect the main piezoresistor channel R_{ch} . The main metrological characteristics of the piezoresistors, such as resistance value R_{chw} , gauge factor K_{chw} , temperature coefficient of resistance α_r^{chw} , and temperature coefficient of sensitivity α_k^{chw} , are determined by the following relationships:

$$R_{chw} = \frac{R_{ch} \cdot R_w}{R_{ch} + R_w} = \frac{\rho_w R_s \cdot L_w}{R_s \cdot H_w + \rho_w \frac{L_w}{L_{ch}}}; \quad (6)$$

$$K_{chw} = \frac{1}{R} \cdot \frac{dR}{d\varepsilon} = \frac{R_s \cdot K_w H_w + \rho_w K_{ch} \frac{L_w}{L_{ch}}}{R_s H_w + \rho_w \frac{L_w}{L_{ch}}}; \quad (7)$$

Figure 3: Sequence of manufacturing operations of high-temperature IPT by SOI method.

Figure 4: Structure of a high-temperature mechanical IPT manufactured by the SOI method

$$\alpha_r^{chw} = \frac{1}{R_{chw}} \cdot \frac{dR_{chw}}{dT} = \frac{R_s \cdot \alpha_r^w \cdot H_w + \rho_w \alpha_r^{ch} \cdot \frac{L_w}{L_{ch}}}{R_s \cdot H_w + \rho_w \cdot \frac{L_w}{L_{ch}}}; \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_k^{chw} = \frac{1}{K_{chw}} \frac{dK_{chw}}{dT} = \frac{R_s \alpha_k^w H_w + \rho_w \alpha_k^{ch} \frac{L_w}{L_{ch}} \frac{K_{ch}}{K_w}}{R_s H_w + \rho_w \frac{L_w}{L_{ch}} \frac{K_{ch}}{K_w}} \quad (9)$$

$$\delta \alpha_k^{chw} = \frac{\alpha_k^w - \alpha_k^{ch}}{\alpha_k^{ch}} \quad (10)$$

where ρ_w is the resistivity of the material of the first wafer in $\Omega \cdot cm$; R_s is the surface resistance of the strain resistor channel in Ω/\square ; L_w and L_{ch} are the number of squares in the topology of the layer R_w to protect the piezoresistor and the piezoresistor channel R_{ch} , respectively, K_{ch} and K_w are the gauge factors of the piezoresistor channel and the material of the first wafer $Wafer_1$, respectively; $\delta \alpha_k^{chw}$ is the relative difference in temperature coefficients of sensitivity between the material $Wafer_1$ and the piezoresistor channel.

Considering that the relative difference in temperature coefficients of sensitivity between the $Wafer_1$ material and the piezoresistor channel R_{ch} primarily depends on the parameters of the R_w layer, when the values of $\frac{\delta \alpha_k^{chw}}{\alpha_k^{chw}}$ are less than 1%, the influence of the layer on the characteristics of the strain gauge channel can be neglected. In that case, the optimal value of the thickness H_w is determined by the following relationship:

$$H_w \leq \frac{\rho_w \cdot L_w \cdot K_{ch}}{R_s \cdot L_{ch} \cdot K_w \cdot \delta \alpha_k^{chw}} \cdot 10^{-2}$$

This relationship ensures that the influence of the R_w layer on the characteristics of the piezoresistor channel remains within an acceptable range.

From the provided considerations, we can draw the following conclusions:

- Insulating properties of p-n junctions at temperatures above $+100^{\circ}\text{C}$ require further study. The current limit of 125°C is not the maximum operating temperature for monocrystalline silicon with insulating p-n junctions.
- Abrupt changes in the temperature dependences of the parameters occur when the junction isolation resistance decreases to a value of $R_{sh} \leq 200R_{in}$. This indicates the need for studying the isolation of piezoresistive channels from the elastic element using a p-n junction layer depleted of charge carriers at temperatures higher than $+100^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- The IPT-SOI design, which includes a monocrystalline silicon elastic element and piezoresistive channels electrically isolated from each other by a glass layer with a matched coefficient of thermal expansion, shows promise for the development of small-sized high-temperature sensors.

In summary, further research is needed to understand the insulating properties of p-n junctions at high temperatures, and the IPT-SOI design with a glass layer is a promising approach for developing high-temperature sensors.

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